

Calculation of Abscissa Variances for the Great-Circle Reductions

L. Lindegren
Lund Observatory

Exact calculation of 'pseudo-variances'

Let $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ be the abscissae of the n stars in a great-circle reduction. This note deals with the problem of assigning a reasonable weight or error estimate to each abscissa.

Strictly speaking, since the abscissa zero point is formally undefined in the great-circle reduction, the abscissa variances are of course *infinite*. On the other hand, any shift-invariant linear combination of the abscissae, such as the relative abscissae $r_i = x_i - x_n$, has a perfectly well-defined variance which may be computed from the normal equations by suitable manipulation. For instance, if we arbitrarily fix the abscissa for one star (the *base star*, here taken to be the n th star), the normals can be solved by standard methods (e.g. Cholesky) after deleting the n th column and row. Inversion of the corresponding $(n-1) \times (n-1)$ matrix gives the correct variance-covariance matrix for the $n-1$ abscissae relative to the base star. However, these variances all depend on the base star in an undesirable way: e.g. if the base star is weak, all variances will be correspondingly large. Moreover, the variance of the base star abscissa is still undefined (or zero, in terms of the relative abscissa).

A much more satisfactory solution is to compute the variances of the n 'centralised' abscissae:

$$\bar{x}_i = x_i - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n x_j, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad [1]$$

These can be written in terms of the $n-1$ relative abscissae r_i as:

$$\bar{x}_i = \begin{cases} r_i - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} r_j, & i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1; \\ -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} r_j, & i = n \end{cases} \quad [2]$$

Once the normal equations matrix for the base-star solution has been Cholesky reduced, the variance of $\bar{x}_i$ can thus be computed by the following procedure: On the right-hand side of the equations, set the j th row equal to the coefficient of r_j in [2], or $\delta_{ij} - 1/n$. After Cholesky reduction of the right-hand side, the variance is obtained as the sum of the squared elements on the right-hand side. The procedure is repeated for each i , including $i = n$.

A practical detail: Before reduction, the right-hand side for computing the variance of $\bar{x}_i$ (with $i < n$) can be written as the sum of the i th unit vector and the constant vector $\mathbf{b} = (-1/n, -1/n, \dots, -1/n)'$. For $i = n$ the right-hand side is simply $\mathbf{b}$. Since the Cholesky reduction is a linear operator, it is thus convenient to make first the reduction of $\mathbf{b}$, save the result and add it to each reduced unit vector. The advantage is of course that the first $i-1$ rows of the unit vectors, being identically zero, need not be reduced.

It can be shown that the variances of $\bar{x}_i$ are in fact identical to the diagonal elements of the generalised inverse (or pseudo-inverse) of the rank defect normal equations matrix for all n stars. For this reason they will be referred to as the 'pseudo-variances' of the abscissae.

The procedure described above is a special case of a more general result demonstrated in NDAC/LO/018 ('Pseudosolution and pseudocovariance for least-squares problems with known null space', Lindegren 1983 April 5). A corresponding procedure is used (very successfully) in the sphere solution for calculating the pseudo-variances of the abscissa zero points.

Statistical prediction of 'pseudo-variances'

The exact computation of all n pseudo-variances according to the method described above requires $\sim fn^3/2$ operations, if f is the filling factor of the normals. With $f \simeq 0.15$, $n \simeq 2000$, and $10 \mu\text{s}$ per operation, the typical computing time is a few hours. If only a fraction F (say) of the pseudo-variances need to be computed exactly, the computing time is reduced approximately by the factor F .

Numerical experiments indicate that the normal equations for the great circle reductions are always quite well-conditioned, apart from the occasional unconnected star (revealed by a singular column). It is then not unreasonable that a large fraction of the variances can in fact be predicted with fair accuracy directly from the diagonal of the normals *before* Cholesky reduction. Figure 1 shows the logarithm of the pseudo-variances (σ_i^2) for a simulated set (LOSIM3) of 1964 abscissae, plotted against the logarithm of $1/d_i$, where d_i is the i th diagonal element of the (unreduced) normal equations matrix. The straight line is the identity relation. Evidently $\sigma_i^2 \geq 1/d_i$ must always hold, but a more interesting result is the very strong correlation between the two quantities, with only a small number of deviants. The shape of the 'curve' defined by the points in Figure 1 suggests a mean relation of the form:

$$\sigma_i^2 = v_0 + \frac{1}{d_i} \quad [3]$$

with v_0 a 'constant' for the set. This relation is tested in Figure 2, where $v_i = \sigma_i^2 - 1/d_i$ is plotted against the logarithm of $1/d_i$. The absence of any significant trend indicates that [3] is indeed a good starting point. v_0 in [3] can be estimated as the mean of v_i for a suitable subset of the stars. In this particular set, $v_0 \simeq 0.0095$.

The scatter about the mean relation [3] must be related to the degree to which each star is connected with other stars in the set (by observations in the same frame), which might perhaps be inferred from an inspection of the normal equations. However, since only the reduced normals were available for the present study, an attempt was made instead to correlate the scatter to some other quantity easily computable from the Cholesky factor. One such quantity is:

$$c_i = \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} R_{ji}^2 + \sum_{j=i+1}^{n-1} R_{ij}^2 \quad [4]$$

where R_{ij} , $1 \leq i < j < n$ are elements of the Cholesky factor above the diagonal. (Note that the diagonal elements of the unreduced normals are also easily obtained from the Cholesky factor as $d_i = \sum_{j=1}^i R_{ji}^2$.)

Figure 3 is a plot of v_i against the logarithm of c_i . Again, there is no visible trend. However, if we plot v_i against the logarithm of c_i/d_i (Figure 4), we find that the largest

scatter occurs for large values of c_i/d_i . In fact, the rms scatter is found to be directly proportional to c_i/d_i (Figure 5), or approximately equal to $1.8v_0c_i/d_i$. It follows that the *relative* statistical uncertainty of the pseudo-variance, as obtained from [3], is approximately given by:

$$\epsilon_i = \frac{1.8v_0c_i}{1 + v_0d_i} \quad [5]$$

Clearly this equation can be used to estimate the uncertainty of a prediction, provided that a reasonable first estimate of v_0 is available. Following an idea developed in NDAC/LO/017 ('Error propagation formulae for Step 1 and 3', Lindegren 1983 Febr 7) we might assume that v_0 is inversely proportional to the *semi-harmonic mean* of d_i , or:

$$v_0 \simeq 0.25 \left(\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} d_j^{-1/2} \right)^2 \quad [6]$$

where the 'slackness parameter' 0.25 was calibrated by means of the present data set LOSIM3. Note that [6] should be used *only* as an initial estimate for [5], and that a more precise v_0 for use in [3] must be obtained as the average of v_i for a reasonable number of stars.

Mixing prediction and exact computation

Based on the methods described in the previous sections, a simple program was written according to the following strategy. It is assumed that only the Cholesky-reduced normals (from the base-star solution) are available.

1. Fix the fraction F of pseudo-variances that you are willing to compute by means of the exact method. The total computing time will be approximately proportional to this number. F may be chosen in the range 0.01 to 1.00.
2. Calculate d_i and c_i for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$. Use [6] to get an initial estimate of v_0 and [5] to compute the uncertainty of the prediction formula for each i . An indexing of the ϵ_i 's is performed according to a non-decreasing sequence.
3. Make a list of the $n_A = 0.75F(n-1)$ abscissae for which the predictions are the most uncertain (largest ϵ_i). Let $\epsilon_{\max}$ be the maximum ϵ_i among the *remaining* abscissae. Add to this list a random selection of $n_B = 0.25F(n-1)$ out of the remaining abscissae with $\epsilon_i \leq \epsilon_{\max}$.
4. Compute exact pseudo-variances for the base star and for the $n_A + n_B$ abscissae in the list. Make a final estimate of v_0 by taking the mean of $\sigma_i^2 - 1/d_i$ for the n_B selected abscissae with $\epsilon_i \leq \epsilon_{\max}$.
5. For the remaining $n - n_A - n_B - 1$ abscissae, use [3] to predict the pseudo-variances. The estimated relative uncertainty of these is taken to be $\epsilon_{\max}$.

The program was run on an HP9000 Series 330 computer at Lund Observatory. Results are shown in Table 1 and Figures 6-10. It appears that a reasonable accuracy of the σ_i 's is obtained already with $F \sim 0.1-0.2$. This accuracy should be quite adequate at least in the early stages of the processing, when the resulting gain in computing time may be particularly valuable.

Table 1 Prediction of standard errors σ_i using an increasing fraction F of exactly computed values. The estimated (relative) uncertainty of the predicted standard errors is given by $\epsilon_{\max}/2$. Actual (relative) errors are defined in the sense $(\sigma_{i,\text{pred}} - \sigma_{i,\text{true}})/\sigma_{i,\text{true}}$, where 'true' values are obtained from the run with $F = 1$.

Fraction F	Computing time (min)	Estimated error (%)	Actual error (%)			Figure
			rms	min	max	
0.01	1.5	33	4.7	-31	+15	6
0.02	3.1	28	4.6	-31	+17	7
0.05	7.4	21	5.9	-28	+27	8
0.10	14.7	16	5.0	-27	+25	9
0.20	29	12	4.0	-20	+24	10
1.00	126	0	0.0	0	0	—

Figure 1. Pseudovariances versus the inverses of the diagonal elements of the (rank deficient) normal equations. The solid line is the identity relation.

Figure 2 (top) and 3 (bottom). The quantity v_i plotted against the diagonal elements of the normals (d_i) and against the c_i number derived from the off-diagonal elements of the Cholesky factor.

Figure 4 (top). The quantity v_i plotted against $\lg(c_i/d_i)$.

Figure 5 (bottom). The rms scatter in the quantity v_i , as function of c_i/d_i . The dashed line is the assumed proportionality.

Pseudo-variance prediction based on 1% sample

Pseudo-variance prediction based on 2% sample

Figure 6 and 7. Comparison between predicted and true standard errors (σ_i) for $F = 0.01$ and 0.02 . The dashed line is the upper uncertainty limit $\epsilon_{\max} / 2$.

Pseudo-variance prediction based on 5% sample

Pseudo-variance prediction based on 10% sample

Figure 8 and 9. Same as before but for $F = 0.05$ and 0.10 .

Pseudo-variance prediction based on 20% sample

Figure 10. Same as before but for $F = 0.20$.